

NOTES

Turbidimetric Studies on the Interaction of Tungstate and Molybdate with Transfusion Gelatin

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A number of physico-chemical methods have been employed to study the interaction of proteins with simple metal ions. However, the reported methods find limited use in the study of the interaction of proteins with polyanions. Difficulty arises due to the complex nature of the polyacids. Their structure changes with slight change in pH over a wide pH range. It is to be noted that not even a single such system has yet been properly elucidated¹.

Investigations described in this paper go to show that turbidimetric method can prove to be of value in such studies particularly in the low pH range, i.e., below the isoelectric point of proteins. The protein chosen for these studies is transfusion gelatin, a well characterized fibrillar protein employed as a blood plasma substitute.

EXPERIMENTAL

Transfusion gelatin (molecular weight 75,000; conc. 6%), henceforth called T.G., supplied by the Director, N.C.L., Poona, was used throughout these investigations. Ammonium paramolybdate (E. Merck) and sodium tungstate (B.D.H.) were dissolved in double distilled water and estimated gravimetrically by oxine method².

The pH 's of the solutions were adjusted with the help of a Cambridge Bench pH -meter using glass electrode and the transmittance noted on Bausch and Lomb spectronic —20 colorimeter at 375 $m\mu$.

Observations were taken with fixed concentration of T.G. and varying concentrations of polyacids and vice versa at pH 's 2, 3 and 4. Ionic strength of the solutions were maintained at 0.2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The inflexion points on the transmittance *vs.* concentration (protein/metal) plots can be used to determine the amount of isopolyacids bound to transfusion gelatin. The

1. Emelius and Anderson, "Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry", English Language Book Society Edition, 1961, p. 315.
2. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", English Language Book Society Edition, 1964, pp. 506 and 567.

binding data so obtained at pH 's 2, 3 and 4 are summarised in the Table No. 1.

TABLE 1

Binding data of tungstate and molybdate with transfusion gelatin

pH	Moles of tungstate	Moles of molybdate
	bound per mole of T.G.	bound per mole of T.G.
2	41.2	52.50
3	46.5	68.25
4	75.0	131.25

From the binding data of tungstate and molybdate with transfusion gelatin it is evident that the respective amounts of polyacid bound per mole of transfusion gelatin decreases with the pH of the system. The amount of molybdate bound to transfusion gelatin is larger than the tungstate. The dependence of binding on pH can be explained on the basis of the existence of differently charged polyanions at different pH 's. The charge on the polyanions increases with the increase in pH ^{3,4} over the range studied and therefore the amount of polyacid bound to positively charged protein should increase.

Below pH 4.6 the transfusion gelatin behaves as positively charged colloid, the amino groups being completely protonated. Tungstate and molybdate molecules exist as negatively charged polyions and thus get themselves electrostatically bound to protein. This kind of binding is further supported by the fact that other polyelectrolytes like detergent ions also combine with protein electrostatically⁵. Moreover this is also borne out of the fact that the insoluble product of the reaction gets peptized on raising the pH of the system. As regards the groups involved in binding the polyacids would react with the protonated ϵ -amino and guanidino groups of lysine and arginine residues in transfusion gelatin. This finds support in the fact that complexes of molybdates with guanidine has been isolated in the pH range 1.4 to 4.5⁶. Reaction with protonated imidazole group can also be visualized but since the histidine residues in transfusion gelatin is negligibly small this possibility can be ruled out.

No turbidity appears above the isoelectric point. Due to this reason interaction of polyacids with transfusion gelatin cannot be followed by this technique. Above the isoelectric point transfusion gelatin becomes negatively charged which would repel negatively

3. Emelius and Anderson, "Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry", English Language Book Society Edition, 1961, p. 310-24.
4. O. P. Sharma, Ph.D. Thesis, 1966, Rajasthan University.
5. F. Putnam, "Advances in Protein Chemistry", Academic Press, 1948, Vol. IV, p. 110.
6. M. P., Rubel. *Zhur. Neorb. Khim.*, 1962, 5, 292.

charged polyacid ions. Even if some binding takes on the positive sites on the protein the overall negative charge on the protein molecules prevent them to coalesce into one another which precludes the appearance of turbidity above the isoelectric pH of the proteins.

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